

Anti-inflammatory potential of sulfurous mineral water and sulfur-containing bioactive compounds: a comparative study*

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Abstract

The therapeutic potential of sulfurous mineral water (SMW) has been recognized since ancient times. Interest in SMW has grown in recent years, particularly regarding its contribution to human health as part of the daily diet. This study aimed to analyze and compare the anti-inflammatory potential of SMW, sulforaphane (SFN), alliin (ALL), and taurine (TAU) in an *in vitro* model of inflammation. The gene expression of cyclooxygenase-2 (*COX-2*), tumor necrosis factor-alpha (*TNF-α*), interleukin-1β (*IL-1β*), and *IL-1β* receptor antagonist (*IL1RN*) was analyzed. In lipopolysaccharide (LPS)-stimulated cells, *COX-2* expression was inhibited in a dose-dependent manner by all compounds, except ALL. *TNF-α* expression was also downregulated, with a more pronounced effect in TAU-treated cells. ALL and TAU, but not SMW and SFN, repressed *IL-1β* during inflammation. SMW, SFN, and ALL, but not TAU, induced *IL1RN* expression. These results suggest that SMW has anti-inflammatory potential mediated by the modulation of selected inflammation-related markers. As expected, an anti-inflammatory effect of SFN, ALL, and TAU was observed in the induced-inflammation model.

Keywords

COX-2, HIEC-6, *IL-1β*, *IL1RN*, sulfur-containing bioactive compounds, *TNF-α*

Introduction

The healing properties of mineral waters have been recognized since ancient times. Their widespread use in balneology, dermatology, and rheumatology has made their anti-inflammatory properties a key focus of scientific research (Bálint et al. 2007; Lee et al. 2012b; Seite et al. 2013; Branco et al. 2016). Sulfur-containing mineral waters are widely distributed, even in areas without volcanic activity, such as Bulgaria. They may differ in activity and application depending on the form of sulfur they contain.

Mineral waters containing sulfur as a sulfate ion (SO_4^{2-}) are classified as sulfate waters. Natural waters containing hydrogen sulfide (H_2S) are classified as sulfurous mineral waters (SMW) (Karagülle and Karagülle 2020). In aqueous solution, H_2S exists alongside its dissociated forms: the hydrosulfide anion (HS^-) and the sulfide anion (S^{2-}). The undissociated form, H_2S , is a lipophilic molecule capable of diffusing across cell membranes and is considered a gas transmitter (Carbajo et al. 2025). In balneology, SMW are used as baths, peloids, inhalations, and drinking therapies to achieve various therapeutic effects (Carbajo

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et al. 2025). Hydropinotherapy with SMW, prescribed as a complementary treatment for patients with specific medical conditions, was reported to improve blood glucose levels and decrease plasma reactive oxygen species (Costantino et al. 2021). The mineral waters from the Varna basin are classified as SMW due to their H₂S content (Vassileva 1996). Additionally, Varna mineral waters are low-mineralized and suitable for daily consumption (Karakolev 1990; Vladeva and Kostadinov 1996, 2007). Analysis of their chemical composition by Sokrateva et al. (2018) revealed significant levels of dissolved sulfides, free H₂S, potassium, selenium, and chromium. Furthermore, in a human intervention study, daily intake of Varna mineral water demonstrated antioxidant and anti-inflammatory potential by increasing total thiol levels in plasma and reducing plasma C-reactive protein (CRP) in healthy volunteers (Roussev et al. 2019; Sokrateva et al. 2021).

Recently, the number of *in vitro* studies involving SMW has risen. Treatment of primary cell cultures or immortalized cell lines with single inorganic molecules, organic components extracted from mineral water, or the whole mineral water demonstrated the potential of these waters to provoke various biological effects, including antioxidant and anti-inflammatory responses (Fioravanti et al. 2013; Gerencsér et al. 2019; Viegas et al. 2019; Silva et al. 2020).

Conversely, plant-derived organosulfur compounds and sulfur-containing amino acids attract significant scientific interest, with their biological effects being the focus of numerous *in vitro* and *in vivo* models and human intervention studies (Petropoulos et al. 2017; Chen et al. 2023; Stoeva et al. 2024). A wealth of scientific data accumulated in recent decades reveals the potential of organosulfides found in broccoli and garlic to contribute to the prevention of various pathological processes, including chronic inflammation, by suppressing the expression and activity of several inflammatory mediators such as cyclooxygenase 2 (COX-2), nitric oxide (NO), interleukin-1 beta (IL-1 β), interleukin 6 (IL-6), and tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α) (Esteve 2020; Lu and Zhao 2020; Kamal et al. 2022).

Sulforaphane (SFN) is one of the most studied isothiocyanates, primarily due to its antioxidant, anticancer, and anti-inflammatory properties (Baralić et al. 2024). It is a dietary organosulfur compound found in plants from the genus *Brassica*, such as cauliflower, broccoli, kale, cabbage, collards, and other cruciferous vegetables (Fahey et al. 2001). Consuming cruciferous vegetables has been linked to a reduced risk of certain metabolic disorders closely associated with low-grade inflammation, such as diabetes (Latté et al. 2011).

Alliin (ALL) and allicin are organosulfur compounds found in garlic. Allicin is the most active, a thioester of sulfenic acid also known as allyl thiosulfinate, synthesized from ALL during the mechanical breakdown of garlic tissue (Ilić et al. 2011; El-Saber Batiha et al. 2020; Stoeva et al. 2024). Garlic organosulfur compounds, including ALL, are reported to attenuate the release of pro-inflammatory mediators in *in vitro* and *in vivo* models of inflammation (Lang et al. 2004; Quintero-Fabián et al. 2013; Shi et al. 2017; Xu et al. 2018).

Taurine (TAU) is a conditionally essential sulfonated beta-amino acid synthesized in the human body from cysteine and is often included in food supplements. Despite being one of the few non-protein amino acids, it is among the most abundant amino acids in the human body. It is found in high concentrations in various tissues, particularly in the brain, retina, muscle tissue, and phagocytic cells. TAU has been reported to act as an antioxidant during oxidative stress-induced inflammation, exhibit cytoprotective effects, and potentially maintain homeostasis during both acute and chronic inflammation (Qaradakhli et al. 2020).

Scientific data accumulated in recent decades reveal the potential of active substances in foods, primarily of plant origin, to suppress inflammatory responses by inhibiting the activity of numerous pro-inflammatory markers in various *in vitro* models (Shan et al. 2009; Lee et al. 2012a; Attiq et al. 2018; Ruhee et al. 2020). However, data comparing the biological effects of sulfur-containing active substances of natural origin on intestinal epithelial cell models are scarce. The gastrointestinal tract is likely the first site where active compounds from foods and water exert their biological effects. Therefore, intestinal cell lines may serve as a valuable model for studying the mechanisms of these effects in both normal and pathological conditions, including inflammation models.

The present study aimed to compare the biological effects of sulfur-containing biologically active compounds (SBAC) from foods and SMW from the Varna basin on human intestinal epithelial cells.

Materials and methods

Mineral water sampling

Twenty-four hours before the analyses, the SMW samples were collected from a public fountain in Varna, Bulgaria, in clean plastic bottles and stored in the dark at 4 °C in a refrigerator. Two hours before the experiment, the water samples were left at room temperature. Immediately before each experiment, a sample of 50 mL SMW was filtered through a 0.2 μ m pore size filter and used to prepare working concentrations with nutritional medium.

Studied compounds, materials, and reagents

L-sulforaphane (Cat. No. 14797) and alliin (Cat. No. 14001) were purchased from Cayman Chemical Company, Ann Arbor, MI, USA. Taurine was obtained from Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc., Waltham, MA, USA (Cat. No. 166540250). Reduced-Serum Medium Opti-MEM™ I with phenol red (Cat. No. 31985-070), phenol red-free Reduced-Serum Medium Opti-MEM™ I (Cat. No. 11058-021), epidermal growth factor (Cat. No. PHG 0311), and GlutaMAX™ Supplement (Cat. No. 35050061) were obtained from Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc. (Gibco, Waltham, MA, USA). Amplifyme SG Universal Mix (Cat. No. AM

02-200) was purchased from Blirt S.A. (Gdansk, Poland). PCR Red Mastermix (Cat. No. M3029.0500) was acquired from Genaxxon Bioscience GmbH (Ulm, Germany). Fetal bovine serum (FBS) (Cat. No. F7524), phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) (pH 7.4) (Cat. No. 806552), Dulbecco's phosphate-buffered saline (DPBS) (Cat. No. 56064C), HEPES (pH 5–6.5) (Cat. No. H3375), and antibiotics were supplied by Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA). Primezol™ reagent (Cat. No. AN1100) was obtained from Canvax Biotech, S.L. (Cordoba, Spain). 3-(4,5-Dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide (MTT) (Cat. No. A2231.0005) was sourced from ITW Reagents, S.R.L. (AppliChem, Monza (MB), Italy). Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) (Cat. No. BP2311) and RevertAid™ First Strand cDNA Synthesis Kit (Cat. No. K1622) were purchased from Thermo Fisher Scientific (Waltham, MA, USA). Trypsin/EDTA 10 × (Cat. No. 392-0459) was procured from VWR (Radnor, PA, USA). Salicylic acid, 99.5% (Cat. No. C351), was supplied by Chintex LTD (Dimitrovgrad, Bulgaria). Lipopolysaccharides (LPS) from *Escherichia coli* (serotype O26:B6, Cat. No. L8274) were provided by Merck (Sigma-Aldrich, Taufkirchen, Germany).

Cell line and subcultivation

The human intestinal epithelial cells HIEC-6 were obtained from the American Type Culture Collection (ATCC® CRL3266™) and cultured in Opti-MEM™ reduced serum medium containing 20 mM HEPES, 10 mM Glutamax, 10 ng/mL epidermal growth factor (EGF), 4% FBS, and a penicillin/streptomycin mixture at final concentrations of 1% for each component. Cells were cultured in 75 cm² flasks and incubated at 37 °C in a humidified atmosphere of 95% air and 5% CO₂.

Cell viability assay

The 3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide (MTT) assay was employed to determine cell viability. The cells were collected and seeded in 12-well flasks using phenol red-free Opti-MEM™ I medium at a density of 6.5×10^4 cells per well. Following 24 h of incubation, the culture medium was removed, and the cells were incubated in fresh medium containing increasing concentrations of SMW (v/v) or SBAC. After 20 h of incubation, 100 µL of MTT working solution (2 mg/mL in PBS) was added to each well, and incubation continued for 4 h. Following the incubation period, the MTT solution was removed, and 1 mL of DMSO was added to each well to lyse the cells and dissolve the formazan crystals. Finally, absorbance was determined using a Synergy 2 plate reader (BioTek) at a wavelength of 550 nm. The viability of the treated cells was expressed as a percentage of the viability of the untreated cells (controls), which was considered 100%. All treatments were performed in triplicate, and data were presented as mean ± SD. Based on the MTT assay, three values of SMW percentage content in the culture medium, along with concentrations of SFN, ALL, and TAU, were selected for further analyses.

Induction of inflammation

HIEC-6 cells were seeded in Opti-MEM™ I medium in 12-well flasks at a density of 6.5×10^4 cells per well. After 24 h, cells were pretreated and incubated for a further 24 h with selected percentage contents of SMW (4, 6, and 8%) and concentrations of SBAC: SFN [µg/mL] 0.5, 1, and 2; ALL [µg/mL] 10, 25, and 30; and TAU [mM] 1, 2, and 5. The cells were treated with 1 µg/mL LPS to induce inflammation. Additionally, 3 mM salicylic acid (SA) was used as a reference compound with anti-inflammatory activity. Each treatment was conducted in triplicate.

Total RNA extraction

After the experiment, the cells were treated with Primezol reagent to isolate total RNA. The protocol adhered fully to the manufacturer's guidelines. Before proceeding to cDNA synthesis, the concentration of isolated RNA from each sample was measured using a multifunctional reader (Synergy 2, BioTek) and was used for cDNA synthesis.

Reverse Transcription

Extracted RNA (200 ng) was reverse transcribed and employed for cDNA synthesis using the First Strand cDNA Synthesis Kit, which contained an oligo (dT)18 primer, reaction buffer, nuclease-free water, RNase inhibitor, nucleotide mix (dNTP), and reverse transcriptase enzyme. The reaction was performed according to the manufacturer's instructions on the GeneAmp PCR System 9700 (Applied Biosystems), with a final reaction volume of 20 µL. Following synthesis, each cDNA sample was diluted with 60 µL of molecular biology-grade water and stored at –20 °C.

Gene expression analysis

The nucleotide sequences of the primers used for analyzing the selected genes are presented in Table 1. The primers were designed using the Real-Time PCR Gene Expression Design Tool and were synthesized by Sigma-Aldrich and Integrated DNA Technologies.

Two-step quantitative real-time PCR was employed to determine the gene expression levels of selected

Table 1. Nucleotide sequences of the primers used.

Target gene (Human)	Nucleotide sequence (5'-3')
<i>Actin-b</i>	F GTG GCC GAG GAC TTT GAT TG
	R CCT GTA ACA ACG CAT CTC ATA
<i>COX-2</i>	F GAA ACA GAG AAG TTG GCA GCA
	R GGC AGG ATA CAG CTC CAC AG
<i>TNF-α</i>	F CTC TTC TGC CTG CTG CAC TTT
	R ATG GGC TAC AGG CTT GTC ACT
<i>IL-1β</i>	F CCA CCT CCA GGG ACA GGA TA
	R AGA ATT AGC AAG CTG CCA GGA
<i>IL1RN</i>	F GCC CAT CCT CAG GAC CTT TC
	R ATG TCC TAG CCA TCC CCA CT

genes in the cell culture. As a template, a preamplifier of 0.50 μL cDNA was used in a final reaction volume of 5 μL . The final concentration of the primers in the reaction mixture was 300 nM. Two-step RT-PCR analysis was performed with the Amplifyme SG Universal Mix kit (Blirt S.A.) using ROX Low fluorescent binding dye. Reactions were conducted in 96-well plates with the following reaction parameters: enzyme activation and denaturation at 95 °C for 3 min; denaturation at 95 °C for 5 s for 40 cycles; annealing at 60 °C for 10 s for 40 cycles; extension and fluorescence detection at 72 °C for 18 s for 40 cycles, followed by melting curve analyses. The analyses were performed on the QuantStudio 5 (Applied Biosystems). For the calculation of gene expression levels, the $2^{-\Delta\Delta\text{Ct}}$ method was applied (Livak and Schmittgen 2001), and mRNA levels were presented as relative units (RU). The expression of genes of interest was assessed by comparison with untreated cells (controls), where the mRNA levels were considered equal to 1. *Actin-b* was used as an endogenous control gene.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analyses were conducted using Microsoft Excel and GraphPad Prism 10.0. One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), followed by Dunnett's test, was applied to compare each treatment group against the control or LPS group. All samples were measured in triplicate, and the mean values were used for analysis. The data are presented as mean \pm standard error of the mean (SEM). A p -value of less than 0.05 indicated a significant difference between the groups.

Results

Cell viability

The effect of SMW and SBAC on cell viability was assessed using the MTT assay. Only concentrations that resulted in a survival rate exceeding 80% were deemed nontoxic. Based on the MTT results (Fig. 1A–D), three concentrations of SMW and each SBAC were chosen for further analyses.

Cell viability decreased sharply compared to the controls ($p = 0.0003$) at the highest percentage content of SMW (20%) in the culture medium (Fig. 1A). However, even at this high concentration of SMW, cell viability remained above 80%. Values between 1% and 16% of SMW content did not significantly alter cell viability. Based on these results, all applied concentrations of SMW were considered nontoxic for HIEC-6. Three concentrations of SMW in the culture medium were selected for further analyses: 4%, 6%, and 8%.

Interestingly, SFN significantly stimulated cell proliferation at 0.25, 0.5, and 1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ (Fig. 1B). However, cell viability noticeably decreased at 5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ SFN. Furthermore, the highest concentration of SFN markedly inhibited cell viability (74%) and may be deemed cytotoxic ($p < 0.001$). Concentrations of 0.5, 1, and 2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ SFN were employed in the subsequent analyses.

As demonstrated in Fig. 1C, the TAU concentrations of 0.2–5 mM did not affect cell viability. The slight decrease in viability of cells treated with 10 mM TAU was not statistically significant (95%, $p = 0.2$). A statistically significant reduction in cell viability was observed in cells treated with 20 mM TAU ($p = 0.03$). Nevertheless, even

Figure 1. Effect of SMW (A), SFN (B), TAU (C), and ALL (D) on HIEC-6 cell viability. Data are presented as mean \pm SD of three independent experiments; * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, and *** $p \leq 0.001$, vs. control (untreated cells).

at this concentration, cell viability remained sufficiently high (89%) to conclude that all TAU concentrations applied were nontoxic to HIEC-6. The TAU concentrations used in the subsequent analyses were 1, 2, and 5 mM. Cell viability in ALL-treated cells (Fig. 1D) significantly decreased at the three highest concentrations. Notably, the viability of cells treated with the highest concentration of 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ approached the 80% threshold. Based on these results, the chosen concentrations of ALL for the subsequent analyses were 10, 25, and 30 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$.

Expression of target genes in a model of LPS-induced inflammation

To explore the anti-inflammatory potential of SMW and SBAC on HIEC-6, a model of LPS-induced inflammation was employed. As detailed in the previous chapter, cells were pretreated for 24 h with the substances under investigation, after which they were exposed to 1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ LPS. Some of the cells were also exposed to the same concentration of LPS alone, without any pretreatment. Furthermore, 3 mM SA was applied as a reference substance known for its anti-inflammatory effects. As previously described, cells were treated with three selected concentrations of each studied compound, in accordance with the MTT assay. The mRNA

levels of *COX-2*, *TNF- α* , *IL-1 β* , and *IL1RN* were compared with those of untreated cells. According to selected concentrations of SMW and SBAC, the following treatment groups were defined: C – control (untreated cells); LPS – lipopolysaccharides; SA – salicylic acid; SMW4, SMW6, SMW8 – cells pretreated with 4%, 6%, or 8% SMW, respectively; SFN 0.5, SFN 1, SFN 2 – cells pretreated with 0.5, 1, or 2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ SFN, respectively; T1, T2, T5 – cells pretreated with 1, 2, or 5 mM TAU, respectively; A10, A25, A30 – cells pretreated with 10, 25, or 30 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ ALL.

Effect of SMW and SBAC on COX-2 expression

Data presenting the potential of SMW and SBAC to influence *COX-2* expression are presented in Fig. 2A–D. As observed, in cells treated with LPS, the gene expression was 1.8-fold higher ($p = 0.0003$). Conversely, SA significantly inhibited the expression of *COX-2*.

Fig. 2A illustrates the mRNA levels of the *COX-2* gene in SMW-treated cells. It was observed that pretreatment with SMW significantly reduced *COX-2* transcription levels in LPS-stimulated HIEC-6. The lowest concentration of SMW significantly decreased mRNA levels in unstimulated cells ($p = 0.05$). Conversely, the highest concentration of 8% SMW

Figure 2. Effect of SMW and SBAC on *COX-2* expression in HIEC-6 under conditions of LPS-induced inflammation. Levels of mRNA are presented as relative units (RU), with untreated cells (controls) taken as 1; cells pretreated with SMW (A); cells pretreated with SFN (B); cells pretreated with TAU (C); cells pretreated with ALL (D); LPS \pm cells without/with LPS-induced inflammation (* $p \leq 0.05$; ** $p \leq 0.01$; *** $p \leq 0.001$ vs. C).

significantly suppressed the expression of the enzyme, both in unstimulated cells and under conditions of induced inflammation, suggesting a concentration-dependent effect of SMW on *COX-2* expression. The effect of SFN on *COX-2* expression was similar (Fig. 2B). Notably, the highest concentration of 2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ inhibited gene expression in both LPS-stimulated and unstimulated cells ($p = 0.037$ and $p = 0.04$, respectively). TAU pretreatment significantly reduced *COX-2* transcription levels in LPS-stimulated HIEC-6 across all three concentrations tested, with this effect being markedly more pronounced in cells treated with the highest concentration (Fig. 2C). None of the applied concentrations of ALL changed the expression levels of the *COX-2* gene (Fig. 2D).

Effect of SMW and SBAC on *TNF- α* expression

Another target pro-inflammatory gene in this study was *TNF- α* . The results illustrating the effect of SMW and SBAC on *TNF- α* expression under conditions of LPS-induced inflammation are summarized in Fig. 3A–D. Similar to *COX-2*, in cells treated with LPS alone, the *TNF- α* gene was significantly overexpressed compared to the control cells ($p = 0.02$). Salicylic acid inhibited the expression of the gene ($p = 0.0047$). The inhibitory effect of SMW on *TNF- α* expression was significant and dependent on its percentage content in the nutrition medium (Fig. 3A). Notably, while unstimulated cells show that only the high-

est concentration exhibits an inhibitory effect on gene expression, all three SMW concentrations demonstrate such an effect under induced inflammation.

TNF- α expression was significantly inhibited in stimulated cells that were pretreated with 1 and 2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ SFN (Fig. 3B). A concentration of 0.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ SFN did not influence the expression of this gene, and its mRNA levels remained comparable to those measured in untreated controls. Taurine demonstrated significant potential to inhibit *TNF- α* expression, both in conditions of induced inflammation and in unstimulated cells, and this effect was concentration-dependent (Fig. 3C). The effect of ALL on *TNF- α* expression was also investigated. In the absence of inflammation, a statistically significant decrease in cytokine expression was observed in cells treated with 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ ALL compared to the control. Under conditions of induced inflammation, a concentration of 25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ significantly reduced mRNA levels (Fig. 3D).

Effect of SMW and SBAC on *IL-1 β* expression

The effect of SMW and SBAC on *IL-1 β* expression is illustrated in Fig. 4A–D. Similar to the previous target genes, LPS significantly stimulated *IL-1 β* gene expression, whereas in cells treated with SA, mRNA levels were notably lower than those in the controls. No change in *IL-1 β* gene expression was observed in SMW- and SFN-treated

Figure 3. Effect of SMW and SBAC on *TNF- α* expression in HIEC-6 under conditions of LPS-induced inflammation. Levels of mRNA are presented as relative units (RU), with untreated cells (controls) taken as 1; cells pretreated with SMW (A); cells pretreated with SFN (B); cells pretreated with TAU (C); cells pretreated with ALL (D); LPS \pm cells without/with LPS-induced inflammation (* $p \leq 0.05$; ** $p \leq 0.01$; *** $p \leq 0.001$ vs. C).

Figure 4. Effect of SMW and SBAC on *IL-1 β* expression in HIEC-6 under conditions of LPS-induced inflammation. Levels of mRNA are presented as relative units (RU), with untreated cells (controls) taken as 1; cells pretreated with SMW (A); cells pretreated with SFN (B); cells pretreated with TAU (C); cells pretreated with ALL (D); LPS \pm cells without/with LPS-induced inflammation (* p \leq 0.05; ** p \leq 0.01; *** p \leq 0.001 vs. C).

cells, with the exception of the unusual upregulation of cytokine expression in SFN 0.5-treated cells (Fig. 4A, B, respectively). In cells with LPS-induced inflammation, TAU demonstrated a statistically significant inhibitory effect on *IL-1 β* mRNA levels (Fig. 4C). At concentrations of 25 and 30 μ g/mL, ALL exhibited an inhibitory effect on *IL-1 β* expression, but only in cells with induced inflammation. No effect of ALL on the expression of this marker was found in the other treatment groups (Fig. 4D).

Effect of SMW and SBAC on *IL1RN* expression

The effects of SMW and SBAC on the gene expression of the anti-inflammatory marker *IL1RN* were investigated (Fig. 5A–D). In cells treated with LPS alone, significantly lower mRNA levels for the gene were observed compared to untreated cells. Salicylic acid had no effect on the gene expression of this marker.

The results presented in Fig. 5 indicate that SMW, SFN, and ALL increased the expression of *IL1RN*, but only in unstimulated cells (Fig. 5A–D). It is worth noting that for ALL, this effect is pronounced, as the *IL1RN* gene was significantly overexpressed at all applied concentrations (Fig. 5D). No changes in mRNA levels were observed in cells treated with TAU (Fig. 5C).

Discussion

For many years, scientific efforts were concentrated on functional foods and nutrition, primarily from plant sources, as sources of active compounds that contribute to human health. In this respect, mineral waters are underestimated as a source of biologically active components for human metabolism, and knowledge of their beneficial effects relies mainly on empirical data.

The mineral water from the Varna basin, classified as SMW due to its H₂S content (Sokrateva et al. 2018), is freely available from public springs within the city. In addition to its use as a remedy for various health problems, this water is widely used as everyday drinking water.

Essentially, *in vitro* studies provide a foundation for exploring the mechanisms of action of various biologically active compounds. They enable rapid and detailed monitoring of changes in target markers following specific treatments. However, despite the rising scientific interest in the beneficial effects of mineral waters and the mechanisms underlying these effects, SMW remains underestimated as part of the daily diet, and the molecular mechanisms of its anti-inflammatory effects are not fully elucidated.

In the present study, SMW and SBAC were compared in terms of their potential to modulate pro- and anti-inflammatory markers in an *in vitro* model of LPS-induced inflamma-

Figure 5. Effect of SMW and SBAC on *IL1RN* expression in HIEC-6 under conditions of LPS-induced inflammation. Levels of mRNA are presented as relative units (RU), with untreated cells (controls) taken as 1; cells pretreated with SMW (A); cells pretreated with SFN (B); cells pretreated with TAU (C); cells pretreated with ALL (D); LPS ± cells without/with LPS-induced inflammation (* $p \leq 0.05$; vs. C).

tion in human intestinal epithelial cells. To the best of current knowledge, this is the first study exploring the anti-inflammatory potential of SMW from the Varna basin in comparison with well-studied sulfur-containing compounds.

Effects of SMW and SBAC on cell viability

The first part of this study focused on determining the range of nontoxic concentrations of all tested substances (Fig. 1A–D). As presented in the Results section, all applied concentrations of SMW could be considered nontoxic, as even at the highest concentration, cell viability remained above the threshold of 80%.

An intriguing result emerged from the SFN cytotoxicity test, revealing that three of the concentrations had a proliferative effect, increasing cell viability to approximately 109% (Fig. 1B). SFN has been extensively researched for its anticancer potential, demonstrated as cytotoxic activity on cancer cell lines (Baralić et al. 2024). Low doses of SFN may enhance cell survival, while high doses of the compound may inhibit cell viability. In this study, the intermediate concentrations stimulated cell proliferation. However, the cell line used in the present study is derived from normal intestinal epithelial cells with intact homeostasis, which likely influences the effects of SFN on cell viability, suggesting that the biological effects of SFN depend on its concentration, cell type, and conditions.

Regarding TAU, cell viability remained unchanged across all applied concentrations. Even at the highest

concentration, where a statistically significant decrease was noted, approximately 90% cell survival was observed (Fig. 1C). Based on these results, all TAU concentrations could be considered nontoxic. The last three concentrations of ALL significantly reduced cell viability. This result was not surprising, as ALL was reported to exhibit high cytotoxic activity *in vitro* across various cancer cell lines, similar to SFN (Zhang et al. 2020; Stoeva et al. 2024). However, in this study, even these high concentrations of ALL did not reduce cell viability below 80%.

In summary, all applied concentrations of SMW, TAU, and ALL can be considered nontoxic to the tested cells. Conversely, SFN exhibits a complex effect on cell viability, stimulating proliferation at the medium concentrations used while displaying cytotoxicity at the highest concentration.

Effects of SMW and SBAC on COX-2 gene expression

The potential of SMW to influence the expression of COX-2 in a model of LPS-induced inflammation was investigated. The results indicated that a 4% concentration of SMW in the nutrient medium inhibited COX-2 expression only in unstimulated cells. However, at the highest percentage content, SMW significantly suppressed the enzyme expression in both unstimulated and LPS-stimulated cells. This effect of SMW on COX-2 gene expression is quite similar to that observed for SFN and TAU (Fig. 2B, C).

The effects observed for SFN were not surprising. Its anti-inflammatory potential has been well demonstrated in various types of *in vitro* models of inflammation, including LPS-stimulated expression of *COX-2* and *TNF- α* (Shan et al. 2009; Ruhee et al. 2020). In addition to these data, the anti-inflammatory effects of SFN were demonstrated in *in vivo* models of lung injury, muscle inflammation, hypoxic pulmonary hypertension, and diabetes (Gu et al. 2017; Ruhee et al. 2020; Pan et al. 2023). Furthermore, several clinical studies have demonstrated the potential of SFN as an adjuvant to anti-inflammatory therapies in humans. Unlike many other plant-derived biologically active compounds, such as polyphenols, SFN has good bioavailability and relatively low toxicity (Houghton 2019; Zuo et al. 2023; Habtemariam 2024).

Dietary TAU is believed to significantly reduce the risk of cardiovascular disease and type 2 diabetes due to its beneficial biological effects, including reducing pro-inflammatory cytokines (Qaradakhli et al. 2020; Swiderski et al. 2023). In this study, TAU suppressed the expression of *COX-2* solely in LPS-stimulated cells, and this effect was concentration-dependent (Fig. 2C). Studies suggest that one potential mechanism underlying the anti-inflammatory effects of TAU relates to its ability to decrease mRNA expression of Toll-like receptor-2, thereby inhibiting the expression of pro-inflammatory cytokines (Miao et al. 2011; Swiderski et al. 2023). Therefore, TAU could be considered a therapeutic agent with the potential to mitigate inflammatory signals.

Cyclooxygenase-2 is the inducible isoform of the enzyme involved in the synthesis of prostanoids (prostaglandins, prostacyclins, and thromboxanes) from arachidonic acid (Zhang et al. 2023). Its expression is induced by various pro-inflammatory stimuli. Unlike the constitutive isoform *COX-1*, the inducible isoform is not subject to biochemical regulation, causing the prostaglandins produced by *COX-2* to lose their beneficial physiological effects and instead act as mediators of acute and chronic inflammation and pain perception (Attiq et al. 2018). For these reasons, *COX-2* is a primary target in the development of nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) based on their inhibitory effect on the enzyme. Most synthetic NSAIDs lack selectivity for the inducible isoform, and thus a significant undesirable effect of their use is ulcer formation. Scientists are focused on creating NSAIDs with high selectivity for *COX-2* and a safer profile to address this issue (Ju et al. 2022). In this context, scientific data on the anti-inflammatory effects of active substances from natural sources, which can potentially suppress the activity or expression of the enzyme, could form the basis for developing new generations of selective NSAIDs without undesirable side effects.

Surprisingly, ALL pretreatment did not affect *COX-2* expression in HIEC-6 at any of the concentrations used. Alongside SFN, ALL has been extensively studied for its anti-inflammatory properties both *in vitro* and *in vivo*. The effects are likely to vary depending on the cell type and the stimulus applied.

Effects of SMW and SBAC on *TNF- α* gene expression

Tumor necrosis factor-alpha is a cytokine recognized as a pivotal regulator of inflammatory processes and is known to be involved in the pathogenesis of several inflammatory and autoimmune diseases (Jang et al. 2021). *TNF- α* can mediate various aspects of inflammation, such as enhancing endothelial cell permeability, thereby facilitating leukocyte migration and the release of other cytokines (You et al. 2021).

In this study, SMW and all SBAC demonstrated potential to suppress *TNF- α* expression; for SMW, SFN, and TAU, this effect was concentration-dependent and pronounced under induced inflammatory conditions. The concentration of 8% SMW and the highest TAU concentration suppressed the expression of the marker in both unstimulated cells and LPS-stimulated inflammation conditions (Fig. 3A, C, respectively). Compared to the control cells, ALL significantly decreased *TNF- α* expression in unstimulated cells treated with 10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and in LPS-stimulated cells treated with 25 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ (Fig. 3D).

There is a substantial body of data in the scientific literature supporting the potential of SFN, TAU, and ALL to suppress *TNF- α* expression. Organosulfur compounds from garlic and cruciferous vegetables exhibit significant anti-inflammatory properties through multiple mechanisms. Sulforaphane, for example, has been shown to alleviate LPS-induced cellular damage in Caco-2 cells by activating the AMPK/SIRT1/PGC-1 α cascade (Zhang et al. 2021). Furthermore, SFN and ALL have been reported to attenuate the expression of pro-inflammatory cytokines by downregulating transcription factors such as NF- κ B and Nrf-2 (Ruhee et al. 2019; Lv et al. 2021).

The anti-inflammatory potential of TAU in inhibiting *TNF- α* is also well documented. Taurine supplementation has been shown to reduce cytokine levels in various contexts, including sepsis models and LPS stimulation (Ma et al. 2022). It has been reported that in stimulated pulmonary macrophages, the TAU metabolite taurine chloride inhibits nuclear factor kappa B (NF- κ B) migration to the nucleus by stabilizing I κ B in the cytoplasm (Barua et al. 2001).

The health benefits of SMW are attributed to its sulfur content, primarily as H₂S and soluble sulfides, which are thought to modulate various biological processes (Carbajo and Maraver 2017; Karagülle et al. 2018; Cheleschi et al. 2020; Carbajo et al. 2025). Several studies have reported the potential of H₂S to affect the activity of transcription factors, such as NF- κ B, and thus to modulate the levels of pro-inflammatory cytokines (Sen et al. 2012; Rios et al. 2015; Bhatia and Gaddam 2021; Shahid and Bhatia 2024). However, it should not be overlooked that SMW also contains components other than H₂S, such as soluble sulfides and micro- and macroelements, which may significantly influence metabolism and contribute to the biological effects.

The observed effects of Varna mineral water are likely attributable to the combined action of all its components. Varna mineral water is a low-mineralized, slightly alkaline thermal water (pH ~7.6). In addition to H₂S, it contains

iron, calcium, magnesium, metasilicic acid, bicarbonates, and sulfates, each of which may drive biological effects at the cellular level. Further studies using mineral waters with different compositions or hydrogen sulfide donors would provide greater clarity regarding the relative contribution of individual components to the observed biological effects in various *in vitro* models.

These data suggest that SMW and SBAC may affect specific targets in multiple signaling pathways while also modulating common markers of pro-inflammatory signals.

Effects of SMW and SBAC on *IL-1 β* gene expression

Interleukin-1 β is a multifunctional pro-inflammatory cytokine that plays a crucial role in both acute and chronic inflammation (Kaneko et al. 2019). It exhibits a pyrogenic effect and has the potential to induce pain signals (Ren and Torres 2009). *IL-1 β* is expressed in a wide range of tissues and various cell types, particularly in macrophages found in lymphoid organs such as the thymus, spleen, lymph nodes, and bone marrow. In non-lymphoid organs, *IL-1 β* is present in tissue macrophages of the lung, digestive tract, and liver and in various specific cell types, including neutrophils, keratinocytes, epithelial and endothelial cells, lymphocytes, smooth muscle cells, and fibroblasts (Kaneko et al. 2019). The binding of *IL-1 β* to its receptor activates several intracellular signaling pathways in target cells. One of the primary effects of transducing these signals is the creation of a pro-inflammatory environment within the cell by the release of a broad network of pro-inflammatory mediators, including cytokines, chemokines, metalloproteinases, acute-phase proteins, prostaglandins, and nitric oxide (Wang et al. 2023).

In this study, TAU and ALL significantly inhibited *IL-1 β* gene expression, but only under LPS-induced inflammatory conditions. This result aligns with data reported by other studies on the therapeutic potential of both SBACs. By contrast, neither SMW nor SFN demonstrated such potential. Conversely, the lowest concentration of SFN in the culture medium (0.5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) unexpectedly up-regulated *IL-1 β* expression. SFN is primarily known for its potent anti-inflammatory properties, reducing *IL-1 β* expression by inhibiting key pro-inflammatory signals such as the NF- κB pathway. However, SFN can induce a mild, temporary (hormetic) pro-inflammatory state as an adaptive response, particularly under caloric challenge in healthy individuals. The potential of SFN to build a stronger defense afterward in the body under mild stress was suggested (van Steenwijk et al. 2023; Djaldetti 2024).

The anti-inflammatory potential of the studied biologically active substances *in vitro* is likely dependent on the target signaling pathways, the model, and the cell type. A class of receptors, known as NLR family pyrin domain containing 3 (NLRP3), expressed in macrophages, is activated by various harmful stimuli, such as reactive oxygen species, crystalline uric acid, and LPS-induced inflammation, subsequently leading to the release of *IL-1 β* . The HIEC-6 cell

line used in this study is fetal, and as a result, specific proteins, including NLRP3, are expressed very weakly or not at all in these cells. A recent study reported that in LPS-stimulated HIEC-6, activation of *IL-1 β* is possible through an NLRP3-independent pathway involving caspase-4 (Chan et al. 2023). It can be speculated that caspase-4 could also be a target of the anti-inflammatory effects of TAU and ALL, a possibility that remains to be confirmed in future studies.

Effects of SMW and SBAC on *IL1RN* gene expression

The *IL-1 β* receptor antagonist is synthesized in response to various pro-inflammatory stimuli, acting as a natural *IL-1 β* inhibitor by competitively binding to its receptor (Kaneko et al. 2019). Once bound to the receptor, *IL1RN* prevents the binding of *IL-1 β* , thereby inhibiting the signaling pathway and reducing the release of several pro-inflammatory factors, including *IL-6*, *IL-8*, and *TNF- α* , therefore playing an important role as an anti-inflammatory mediator (Lutotola 2022; Villatoro et al. 2023; Wang et al. 2023). Research has demonstrated that the inhibition of *IL1RN* results in an increase in pro-inflammatory signals and tissue damage. Thus, the balance between *IL-1 β* and *IL1RN* is crucial for maintaining a robust anti-inflammatory status (Ortiz et al. 2007; Cardoso et al. 2022; Maculewicz et al. 2022). Given the scientific evidence supporting a physiological relationship between these two markers and the regulatory role of *IL1RN* on *IL-1 β* activity, it can be inferred that *IL1RN* itself could serve as a potential target for the development of new anti-inflammatory drugs (Kaneko et al. 2019).

In this study, overexpression of *IL1RN* was detected in cells pretreated with SMW, SFN, and ALL, but only in unstimulated cells. This result highlights the potential of these natural compounds to enhance immune defense in uncompromised cells, which is likely to increase their resistance and survival when pro-inflammatory stimuli are present.

Studies examining the factors influencing transcriptional regulation and the relationship between *IL-1 β* and *IL1RN* are relatively scarce. The results obtained in the present study provide a valuable contribution to clarifying this relationship and enhancing understanding of the anti-inflammatory potential of biologically active substances of natural origin, including SMW and SBAC.

In summary, this study examined the potential of SMW from the Varna basin to influence the expression of markers related to the inflammatory response. The results discussed above indicated that SMW should be considered a potential source of biologically active components together with organosulfur compounds known for their well-established anti-inflammatory properties.

This study has several limitations. No dedicated physicochemical analysis was conducted for each SMW sample. Instead, mineral composition was derived from previously published data for the same source (Sokrateva et al. 2018), which may not capture potential variability. Therefore, the results should be considered hypothesis-generating.

Finally, the use of fetal HIEC-6 cells may limit the interpretation of the findings, as certain proteins and signaling pathways may be weakly expressed or absent, which could influence the magnitude of the observed effects.

Conclusion

The results obtained confirm the data on the anti-inflammatory potential of SFN, ALL, and TAU, revealing the ability of SMW to inhibit the expression of genes related to the inflammatory response, both under LPS-induced inflammation and in unstimulated cells. For SMW from the Varna basin, these results are the first scientific data of their kind supporting understanding of its anti-inflammatory effect and its potential to modulate gene expression related to the inflammatory response in intestinal cells. The results obtained in this study contribute to enhancing understanding of the effects of active substances from food and mineral waters on the markers associated with the inflammatory response. These findings may also assist in developing new strategies for personalized nutrition, with implications for human health.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

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The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

Use of commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines: HIEC-6 were obtained from the American Type Culture Collection (ATCC® CRL3266™).

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

No AI tools were used in the preparation of this manuscript.

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Author contributions

Conceptualization: M.N. and T.S.; methodology: M.N., M.P., and D.V.; validation: M.N. and T.S.; formal analysis: M.N.; investigation: M.N., S.S., D.V., and M.P.; writing—original draft preparation: M.N. and T.S.; writing—review and editing: M.N., D.V., and T.S.; visualization: M.N.; supervision: M.N.; project administration: M.N. and S.S.; funding acquisition: M.N.

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Data availability

The original contributions presented in this study are included in the article. Further inquiries can be directed to the corresponding author.

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